

EBFMC25-OOP-08 · An Adult Case of Posterior Urethral Valve: Symptoms, Diagnosis, Management and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Congenital lower urinary tract obstruction is a clinical entity which is mostly encountered intrauterine or in childhood. In approximately 60% of cases, the cause is posterior urethral valve (PUV) (Capone V., et al.,2022). The incidence of PUV is estimated to be approximately one in 7000-8000 births (Malin G., et al.,2012; Thakkar D., et al., 2014). PUV is one of the most important life-threatening congenital anomalies in the neonatal period. According to a systematic review, PUVs are responsible for approximately 32% of chronic renal failure (CRF) and 20% of end-stage renal failure (ESRF) (Hennus P.M., et al., 2014). While the usual clinical presentation is intrauterine, perinatal, neonatal and childhood problems, PUV cases presenting in the adult period may also be encountered as in our case. Our aim in this case report is to draw attention to the fact that PUV cases may also be encountered in adult patients and that these patients can be treated effectively with clinical suspicion and appropriate evaluation.

Case Presentation: A 39-year-old male patient was admitted to our clinic with complaints of difficult, thin, painful and difficult micturition. He stated that his complaints had been present since childhood, that he could not get any result from his previous (childhood) applications and that his voiding was not relieved. Urethroscopy revealed an appearance compatible with type 1 posterior urethral valve. The patient underwent valve incision with a cold knife.

Discussion: Both our case and other cases in the literature show that not all PUV cases may be diagnosed in infancy and/or childhood. Undoubtedly, there is a risk of ESRD in patients with infravesical obstruction. However, in cases with tolerable obstruction as in our case, patients may suffer from lower urinary tract symptoms only without the development of ESRD.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be kept in mind that patients presenting to urology clinics with unresolved voiding problems may have undiagnosed congenital pathologies.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Posterior urethral valve, urinary obstruction, disuria

INTRODUCTION

Congenital lower urinary tract obstruction is a clinical entity which is mostly encountered intrauterine or in childhood. In approximately 60% of cases, the cause is posterior urethral valve (PUV) (Capone V., et al.,2022). The incidence of PUV is estimated to be approximately one in 7000-8000 births (Malin G., et al.,2012; Thakkar D., et al., 2014). PUV is one of the most important life-threatening congenital anomalies in the neonatal period. According to a systematic review, PUVs are responsible for approximately 32% of chronic renal failure (CRF) and 20% of end-stage renal failure (ESRF) (Hennus P.M., et al., 2014). In children, 17% of ESRD can be attributed to PUVs (Hodges S.J., et al., 2009). Currently, Hampton Young classification is frequently used in PUV classification (Young H.H., et al., 2002). Among the 3 types of PUVs mentioned in Young classification, type 1 and type 3 PUVs are obstructive. 90-95% of the cases are type 1 valves. In the most common type 1 valves, there is a protrusion extending at the base of the urethra, continuing with the verumontanum, going anteriorly and separating into two fork-like protrusions at the bullo-membranous

junction (Young H.H., et al., 2002). Type 3 valves are located at different levels of the posterior urethra and have no relation with the verumontanum. The valve tissue adhering to the entire circumference of the urethra with a small opening in the centre obstructs the lumen (Malin G., et al., 2012). While the usual clinical presentation is intrauterine, perinatal, neonatal and childhood problems, PUV cases presenting in the adult period may also be encountered as in our case. Our aim in this case report is to draw attention to the fact that PUV cases may also be encountered in adult patients and that these patients can be treated effectively with clinical suspicion and appropriate evaluation.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 39-year-old male patient was admitted to our clinic with complaints of difficult, thin, painful and difficult micturition. He stated that his complaints had been present since childhood, that he could not get any result from his previous (childhood) applications and that his voiding was not relieved. Physical examination revealed no pathological clinical signs. Uroflowmetry revealed a split voiding pattern and the mean flow rate was 7 ml/sec (Figure 1).

The amount of residual urine after voiding was 45 cc. Overactive bladder symptom score was 19 and IPSS score was 10/3. Urodynamic examination was also performed. There was difficulty in insertion of the urethral catheter. No pathology was observed in the filling phase of urodynamics. Sensation, capacity and compliance were normal. In the voiding phase, increased pelvic floor muscle activity was observed during micturition. Cystoscopy was planned. On cystoscopy, the bladder was normal, ureteral orifices were in natural position and clear coloured urine jets were seen. Urethroscopy revealed an appearance compatible with type 1 posterior urethral valve. The patient underwent valve incision with a cold knife (Figure 2).

Figure 2

The operation time was 30 minutes. Bleeding and complications were not observed. The patient was discharged on postoperative day 2 and urethral catheter was removed on postoperative day 4. Clinical improvement was observed at follow-up. Uroflowmetry showed great improvement on voiding curve (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Late symptomatic PUV clinic is encountered as case reports in the literature. For example, in the study in which an 11-year-old child and a 40-year-old male patient were presented in the early 2000s, PUV was detected while the 11-year-old child was investigated for intermittent and low-pressure voiding complaints and his clinic completely improved after valve ablation. In a 40-year-old male patient who had recurrent urinary tract infections and painful and difficult voiding complaints that could not be resolved since childhood, PUV was diagnosed in a similar manner and dilatation in the posterior urethra was observed on voiding cystourethrography and PUV was diagnosed, and the patient's complaints completely resolved after the diagnosis was confirmed and valve ablation was performed (Jesus, C. M., Trindade Filho, J. C., & Goldberg, J., 2008). In a case reported from our country in 2010, PUV was found and resected on endoscopic imaging in a patient of similar age and with similar clinical complaints. It was observed that the patient's clinical complaints improved completely after the procedure (Kilciler, M., et.al., 2010). One of the most remarkable cases in the literature about PUV in adults is a 67-year-old male patient who had many physician visits for lower urinary tract complaints for 40 years and did not benefit from the treatments. In this case, complete

recovery was achieved with ablation of PUVs found on endoscopic examination and resection of the bladder neck (Hosseini, J., Ansari Djafari, A., & Hojjati, S. A., 2021). An interesting case recently presented is a case of PUV in an 18-year-old young man who presented to the emergency department with general deterioration and renal dysfunction and was found to have neglected enuresis nocturna on further evaluation. The patient was a professional basketball player who deteriorated after training and was found to have elevated blood pressure and chronic renal failure in the emergency department; on further evaluation, it was understood that he had neglected enuresis nocturna and eventually bladder outlet obstruction, bladder diverticula, bilateral hydronephrosis and chronic renal failure developed due to PUV (Liu, V. S., Qureshi, M. A., & Aziz, M. A., 2024).

DISCUSSION

Both our case and other cases in the literature show that not all PUV cases may be diagnosed in infancy and/or childhood. Therefore, PUV, which is a common obstructive pathology in childhood, may also be encountered in the adult patient group. These cases may present with basic urological symptoms (dysuria, frequent urination, etc.) or as delayed cases with established renal damage. Especially in patients with clinical suspicion, uroflowmetry evaluation, careful evaluation of the voiding curve, and the use of advanced diagnostic tests such as voiding cystourethrography and cystoscopy are important. Undoubtedly, there is a risk of ESRD in patients with infravesical obstruction. However, in cases with tolerable obstruction as in our case, patients may suffer from lower urinary tract symptoms only without the development of ESRD.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be kept in mind that patients presenting to urology clinics with unresolved voiding problems may have undiagnosed congenital pathologies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Capone, V., Persico, N., Berrettini, A., Decramer, S., De Marco, E. A., De Palma, D., ... & Montini, G. (2022). Definition, diagnosis and management of fetal lower urinary tract obstruction: consensus of the ERKNet CAKUT-Obstructive Uropathy Work Group. *Nature Reviews Urology*, 19(5), 295–303.
- Hennus, P. M., de Kort, L. M., Bosch, J. L. H., de Jong, T. P., & van der Heijden, G. J. (2014). A systematic review on the accuracy of diagnostic procedures for infravesical obstruction in boys. *PLOS ONE*, 9(2), e85474.
- Hodges, S. J., Patel, B., McLorie, G., & Atala, A. (2009). Posterior urethral valves. *The Scientific World Journal*, 9(1), 1119–1126.
- Hosseini, J., Djafari, A. A., & Hojjati, S. A. (2021). Adult Posterior Urethral Valve: a Case Report of the Oldest Known Patient. *Men's Health Journal*, 5(1), e13–e13.
- Jesus, C. M. N. D., Trindade Filho, J. C. D. S., & Goldberg, J. (2008). Late presentation of posterior urethral valve: two case reports. *São Paulo Medical Journal*, 126, 126–127.
- Kilciler, M., Basal, S., Irkilata, H. C., Zor, M., Istanbuluoglu, M. O., & Dayanc, M. (2010). Adult posterior urethral valve: a case report. *GMS German Medical Science*, 8, Doc08.
- Liu, V. S., Qureshi, M. A., & Aziz, M. A. (2024). Posterior Urethral Valves in a Healthy-Appearing Athletic Adult: A Case Report. *Cureus*, 16(8).
- Malin, G., Tonks, A. M., Morris, R. K., Gardosi, J., & Kilby, M. D. (2012). Congenital lower urinary tract obstruction: a population-based epidemiological study. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 119(12), 1455–1464.

Thakkar, D., Deshpande, A. V., & Kennedy, S. E. (2014). Epidemiology and demography of recently diagnosed cases of posterior urethral valves. *Pediatric Research*, 76(6), 560–563.

Young, H. H., Frontz, W. A., & Baldwin, J. C. (2002). Congenital obstruction of the posterior urethra. *The Journal of Urology*, 167(1), 265–267.

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